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CONCEPT FOR EXTERNAL QUALITY ASSURANCE OF AN INSTITUTE'S COURSE PORTFOLIO

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ABSTRACT

In most manufacturing firms, processes and products undergo continuous and often rigorous quality assurance (QA). Such QA-systems ensure that products adhere to quality standards and specifications. In addition, a firm's sales numbers are a direct measure of the continuous relevance and attractiveness of the firm's products.

Universities 'produce' courses. Some courses teach fundamentals (e.g. mathematics and physics), while others teach specific methods for application in graduates' future careers. Ideally, the skillset that students receive from the specific-method-courses should continuously develop. However, courses often run for decades without enacting necessary changes, and when change happens, the reasons are often student dissatisfaction or new instructors. Most universities have elaborate systems for student evaluations, while inputs from employers and the wider society are scarce. Skillsets must develop in concert with employer needs, technological progress, and the wider needs of society.

This paper presents a system for course quality assurance (CQA-system) developed at the center for bachelor of engineering studies at the Technical University of Denmark. The CQA-system is inspired by manufacturing industries, where quality assurance has a long history. The system includes a four-step process for the quality

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assurance of individual courses, a procedure for selecting courses for review, and principles for organizing the overall effort in an institute's management infrastructure.

1 INTRODUCTION

In manufacturing industries, quality is an ever present focus since customer demand for quality product is always present. To meet the demand, manufacturers are certified to various quality standards that ensure that quality is built into every aspect of the company's activities. All activities are documented and audited/reviewed in a structured and systematic way to ensure quality in both products and services.

In universities, the assurance of quality often occurs at more overall (superficial) levels where audits and reviews concern entire educations rather than specific courses. Deepening the quality assurance of university educations, requires a system developed to ensure the right quality all the way down to individual courses.

The inspiration for developing such a system is found in the traditional approach for quality improvement projects. In Lean manufacturing and industrial quality standards the approach Plan – Do – Check – Act (Deming circle) [1] is often used as basis for designing a systematic and structured method for improving quality. This approach also constitutes the foundations for the course quality assurance system (CQA-system) presented in this paper. The CQA-system ensures quality for 'customers' of the individual courses.

The motivation behind developing the system was an interest in making the best educated engineering students in Europe by developing graduate skillsets that match current employer demands as well as future demands and the needs of society at large.

1.1 Overall requirements of successful QSA-systems

To operate successfully, a CQA-system must function as a systematic and structured process for all system activities. Furthermore, the system must function in an awarding and positive atmosphere that inspires participant engagement and fosters receptive attitude. The system must include a process of selecting the relevant individual courses for review and nominating the right set of persons for a review panel. Nominating the review panel must be a careful process that matches the experience and job positions of panel lists with the content and purpose of a course selected for review. The course reviews must follow a structured process that leads to the identification of the right changes. Finally, review outcomes must be documented, so learnings are kept and can be applied. Knowledge that is transferable to other courses, must be conveyed to the responsible instructors and institute management.

2 THE CHALLENGE OF ENSURING CONTINUOUS COURSE QUALITY AND RELEVANCE

When examining how individual courses are updated and how often they accommodate changes in theory, models, technologies, etc., it appears that courses are often only updated when the instructor changes or when the course receives poor ratings or complaints. Since instructors often teach the same course for years and years, universities face an uphill battle in continuously ensuring a match between the skillset a course teaches and the needs of current and future employers as well as society at large.

One reason for widening mismatches is that instructor's year-by-year lose their connection with the development and changes in fast evolving industrial sectors, when their primary focus is their job of teaching. Therefore, implementing and operating a CQA-system that continuously ensures quality and relevance, is needed.

3 REQUIREMENTS FOR CQA-SYSTEMS AND THE PITFALLS OF IMPLEMENTING THE SYSTEM

This section details the requirements of CQA-systems and implementation pitfalls.

3.1 Trust and psychological safety

Reviews are conducted in group sessions with participants in different places in their professional lives. So, the experience and social status among reviewers as well as reviewees differs. These differences impact participant openness, which is counterproductive for the right review outcomes. In addition, instructors who are subjected to a review often feel nervous and may perceive the review as an exam. To get the best review outcomes, all parties involved must feel safe [2], both when signing up for the review as well as during the process. Only with trust and psychological security, people will open up and speak freely without bias about their course and the topics that surface during the review.

3.2 Anchoring the CQA-system in the overall management infrastructure

As with any other part of a Quality Management system, the focus and support of upper management is an absolute requirement [3]. Management must activate and promote the CQA-system. Focus and organization-wide involvement is ensured by management involvement. Upper institute management should be present or at least represented among the participants in the review panel.

3.3 Fostering a continuous improvement culture

Motivation for developing and operating a CQA-system that ensures the highest quality and relevance in engineering education should be a heartfelt wish among all educators. "Greatness attracts talent". By being and striving for high course quality and relevance, the institute can attract great instructors and motivate students. A continuous quality improvement effort may call for a change in culture. In particular, a new approach to course updating and maintenance. In the end, a result may be a

new perception of engineering courses that results in combinations of fundamental skills in mathematics and physics, and cutting-edge skills that employers need.

4 THE CQA-SYSTEM AND ITS ELEMENTS

This section details the individual elements that together comprise the CQA-system.

4.1 Selection of courses for review

The selection of courses follows a structured sequence of prioritization and selection:

1. A rough division is made between courses that offer fundamental skills as mathematics and physics, and courses that teach specific skills for direct application on graduates' future careers. The latter group is the focus of the CQA-system.
2. The portfolio of courses for one education is scrutinized for courses relevant for review
3. A priority of course reviews is set

The prioritization is made using a combination of different criteria. These may differ slightly among universities depending on the balance of the research v. practice orientation scale. Examples of criteria are:

- Courses with substantial amounts of methods and models for direct career application
- Courses where technology and methods are undergoing rapid changes
- Courses that are a part of the identity (key courses) on an education

To ease the process of starting up the reviews, one approach is a call for instructors, who voluntarily wish to participate. As the CQA-system shows results, other instructors 'warm up' to the system and in the next stage selection can take place using the selection criteria. To ensure that all selected courses will undergo a review, a time frame for the review process has been set to be max five years.

4.2 Principles for ensuring a positive atmosphere for participation

To have successful and valuable outcomes of the process, the right working atmosphere is essential. One part of establishing this atmosphere is selecting the right pilot courses with cooperating instructors that are eager to have their course reviewed. For the review itself, setting the scene and clarifying condition under which the review will be held must be clear. First of all, a management participant and the internal review manager must emphasize that all meetings are held with a positive 'we want to learn' approach. A review is not a blame-game or a matter of pointing out what is wrong. Rather, the focus is on how the course can be improved. The aim is to focus on the positive things that can be added/changed to better match technological development and employer needs. Also important is to articulate how the course will benefit in the future after implementing changes.

The dialogue must be based on curiosity and avoid arguing. This will create a positive and creative atmosphere leading to great input on improvement and changes.

4.3 Selecting the review panel

The nomination of the review panel is a meticulous process. The goal is to have a broad spectrum of participants in the review panel. Ideally, a mix of seniority, branches of industry, and experience within the fields of the course topics. The panel should consist of several groups:

- Students who are either participating in the course or have just finished the course. Students are chosen on their track record, engagement in the course and their social skills. The students are urged to get opinions from their fellow students prior to the review thus ensuring the largest amount of input from students possible.
- External candidates from industry representing employers. These panel participants are often found through the personal network of the instructor or fellow colleagues. The preferred candidates have completed the course themselves and have worked with topics related to the course under review.

The total group of external review panelists should represent several industry branches or employer groupings. The aim is to ensure experience and course-knowledge of the individual panelists, and representation of a variety of industries or employer groupings from the total panel.

Part of the institute's upper management is invited to the review panel as well. The purpose is to show to the rest of the university that this is an important issue concerning the university's aim to offer the best and most relevant education. Furthermore upper management participation shows engagement in the review as well as having a chance to get information about what is really going on at the teaching level of the institute.

4.4 The review process for individual courses

Prior to the review, panelists are notified about their co-panelists, time and place for the review meeting. Shortly after, they will receive a description of the course and a lecture plan. The description of the course contains the following elements:

- General course objectives
- Objectives for learning outcomes
- Literature and readings
- The lecture plan

The lecture plan details all lectures, content and exercises described fairly detailed (3-4 pages). Panelists are asked to read the papers and prepare questions and opinions on the material.

The review meeting starts with a presentation of the purpose of the meeting and framing the plan for the meeting. Then, panelists make short presentations of

themselves with information on their professional life and careers. This is followed by a presentation of the course by the instructor. This presentation provides in-depth information on the individual lectures. After the presentation the review board is encouraged to suggest themes for discussion. Each theme is then discussed and during the discussion, the instructor takes notes on any new subjects, methods and tools being brought forward. During the session, potential exclusion of current course elements are also evaluated. The review meeting finishes with an oral summary of the points discussed by the instructor. The instructor writes up a report that details the themes discussed and other findings. This report is then sent to all panelists for approval. Upon approval, the report is sent to the head of studies and the person responsible for the course (often this is the instructor, but it can be others).

Figure 1 Flow chart activities

4.5 Decisions about changes

Decisions about how to develop the course is taken on a meeting with the management of the faculty, the institute's head of studies, and the instructor. The report is discussed and the opinions and experience of the review panel is taken in consideration when taking decisions on what to change. A short report on the decisions made is written and sent to all parties involved and the upper management.

4.6 Implementing changes and follow-up

The implementation of changes/improvements is done by the instructor by changing the material for the course and the lecture plan. If needed, the official description of the course will be changed as well. This will be done as soon as possible. During the next run of the course, a midterm evaluation and an end term evaluation is conducted. These evaluations focus especially on feedback from students on the changes made to the course. The feedback in the evaluation is discussed with the students to clarify issues/opinions brought up.

4.7 General learnings for other courses

During the discussion on which changes to implement it is also discussed whether the changes present learning relevant for other parts of the university. If so, these points are reported to the dean of education.

4.8 Anchoring the CQA-system in the institute's management infrastructure

To make sure the whole university benefits from implementing the CQA-system, the system should ideally be implemented across all institutes in the university. It should be an integral part of the university's educational quality assurance system [4]. This system ensures not just the quality and relevance of courses, but naturally contributes to the upgrade to the newest knowledge within a field.

5 EXPERIENCES FROM APPLICATION AT DTU ENGINEERING TECHNOLOGY

The experiences at DTU Engineering Technology (the center for bachelor of engineering studies at the Technical University of Denmark) have been a fruitful learning experience for both instructors and employers. Employers feel they are being heard about both their current demands for graduates as well as their expected needs for future skillsets.

The one challenge that rose from the pilot runs of the CQA- system concerned the implementation of new topics into a course's lecture plan. These lecture plans are already fully packed, so when panelists suggest new topics, something needs to go. Excluding topic is often a tough choice.

It is also clear that students' learning experience during their education does not always fit perfectly with their career needs. One example is students questioning the importance of delivering oral presentations ("too much and too often"). By contrast, the review panelists pointed out how important it is for an engineer to be able to present and explain topics with differing complexity to a broad set of employees and management levels. Training this discipline is crucial for career success and panelists emphasized how presentation skills was not an area for compromise.

6 CONCLUSION: CQA-SYSTEM SUMMARY

When building a system for continuous quality assurance of an institute's course portfolio it is important that the system is systematic, transparent and structured. The process starts with selection of courses. The right courses that need continuous quality assurance are courses that (a) teach specific methods and models for direct career application, (b) where technology and methods undergo rapid changes, and (c) courses that are key courses on an education. When selecting the review panelists, the preferred set of participants has mixed levels of seniority, represents different branches of industry, and has experience within the field of the course. During the review, a safe atmosphere and positive mindsets are crucial for successful and valuable outcomes. The focus must be improvement potentials. Outcomes cannot be successful if the review process is a blame-game or pointing out what is wrong. Anchoring the learnings from the review process has to be done both locally in the course and on a university level. Ideally, the CQA-system should be implemented across all institutes in the university as well as being integrated in the university's educational quality assurance system.

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